

PROBE WG2 “Advanced ABL profiling” - Deliverable 2.1

Humidity and temperature

D2.1: Reports, white and review papers on key ABL parameters, their applications, and the end-user requirements.

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Project title (acronym)	Deliverable 2.1, Product: Humidity and Temperature
Authors	Document preparation conducted by P. Martinet Authors (by alphabetical order): D. Cimini, P. Martinet, U. Löhnert, T. Marke, D. Turner

1 INTRODUCTION

This section focuses on ABL temperature and humidity profiles presenting an overview of the product capabilities (accuracy, uncertainty estimates, readiness for operation etc...). Existing processing chains are also reported and published references are listed so that the reader can get more details on specific aspects if necessary.

2 PRODUCT OVERVIEW

Continuous Temperature and humidity profiling from ground is commonly based on passive microwave and infrared instruments and active lidar systems. Each type of instrument has its own advantages and limitations.

Active sensors provide vertical profiles with a better vertical resolution but cannot provide information within and above clouds due to the attenuation of the lidar signal. They also suffer from a “blind zone” which is in general between the surface and 50 m or as high as a few hundreds of meters.

Passive instruments do not suffer from any blind zone which makes them sensitive to the very lowest layers of the atmosphere but have a coarser vertical resolution compared to active instruments. Hyperspectral infrared spectrometers provide more information on the vertical structure compared to microwave radiometers but their signal is totally attenuated within optically thick clouds similarly to lidars. Microwave radiometers have the possibility to provide vertical profiles in all-sky conditions well resolved for temperature in the boundary layer but with a poor description of the vertical structure for water vapor.

In this section the following acronyms are used:

- MWR: microwave radiometer (20 to 60 GHz spectral bands)
- DIAL: Differential Absorption Lidar (wavelength depending on the DIAL system)
- Raman lidar (typical laser wavelength of 355 nm)
- IRS: Infrared Spectrometer (~ 3 to 20 μm)

For MWR and IRS, two types of retrieval algorithms exist: statistical retrievals (neural network, statistical regularization method¹⁷, linear and quadratic regressions) based on a training dataset dependent on the site and physically-based algorithms (called OEM for optimal estimation methods) that do not need a training but combine the observations with an a priori information of the atmospheric state (either from a short-term-forecast or from a climatology of profiles).

3 PRODUCT OVERVIEW

Products	Temperature profile	Humidity Profile
Instruments	- Below cloud: MWR, IRS, Raman lidars - Within and above cloud: MWR	- Below cloud: Raman lidars, DIAL, IRS, MWR - Within and above cloud: MWR
Accuracy requirements	- WMO OSCAR requirements ²⁵ : 0.5 K (goal) and 1 K (breakthrough)	- WMO OSCAR requirements ²⁵ : 2% (goal) and 5% (breakthrough)
Temporal resolution Requirement	- NWP applications : 30 minutes - Nowcasting applications: 6 minutes - Process studies: 1 minute	- NWP applications : 30 minutes - Nowcasting applications: 6 minutes - Process studies: 1 minute
Applications	- Data assimilation - Process studies - Validation of satellite products - Weather nowcasting	

<p>End-Users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Weather services - University (Academy) - Space agency - Private companies (wind energy sector) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Weather services - University (Academy) - Space agency
<p>Existing algorithms</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>For MWRs alone:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IPT (Cologne University): OEM retrieval using a climatology as the “a-priori”⁵ - Net1D (Météo-France/IMAA)³: OEM retrieval using a NWP model short-term forecast as the “a priori” - Statistical regularization method¹⁷ (for single channel MWR): physically-based retrieval using temperature autocorrelation matrix calculated from a climatology of radio soundings as the “a-priori” - TROPoe (NOAA)¹: OEM retrieval using a climatology as the “a-priori” - Neural network: provided by manufacturers for each MWR unit and implemented in the MWRpy²⁶ processing chain; trained from either a climatology of radiosoundings or model re-analyses - Linear / quadratic regressions trained either from a climatology of radiosoundings or model re-analyses: can be provided by manufacturer or the MWRpro²⁵ chain provided by the university of Cologne - <u>For IRS alone:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> TROPoe¹: OEM retrieval using a climatology as the “a-priori” - <u>For Raman lidar:</u> no need for advanced algorithms, the temperature profile is derived directly from the ratio of the pure rotational Raman channels. - <u>For synergistic retrievals:</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. TROPoe² allows combination from IRS/ MWR and Raman lidars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>For MWRs alone:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IPT (Cologne University): OEM retrieval using a climatology as the “a-priori”⁵ - Net1D (Météo-France/IMAA)³: OEM retrieval use a NWP model short-term forecast as the “a priori” - TROPoe (NOAA)¹: OEM retrieval using a climatology as the “a-priori” - Neural network: provided by manufacturers for each MWR unit and implemented in the MWRpy²⁶ processing chain; trained from either a climatology of radiosoundings or model re-analyses - Linear / quadratic regressions trained either from a climatology of radiosoundings or model re-analyses: can be provided by manufacturer, or the MWRpro²⁵ chain provided by the university of Cologne - <u>For IRS alone:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> TROPoe¹: OEM retrieval using a climatology as the “a-priori” - For DIAL and Raman Lidar²³: no need of advanced algorithm, the water vapor mixing ratio is directly derived from the ratio of the power received by the instrument at two wavelengths -Relative Humidity from Raman lidar: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Using OEM approach (MeteoSwiss)¹² - <u>For synergistic retrievals:</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. TROPoe²: allows combination from IRS/MWR/Raman lidars and DIAL 3. OEM for Raman lidar and MWR (MeteoSwiss)²⁴
<p>Assumptions needed</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For Raman lidar calibration: calibration is done against an external reference, typically a radiosonde or a MWR profile. Assumptions include proximity of reference measurement in space and time and/or homogeneous 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For Raman lidar calibration: absolute calibration is done against external reference, typically a radiosonde profile or a total column measurement from MWR or GPS. Assumptions include proximity in space and

	<p>atmosphere.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For MWR: horizontal homogeneity in area around ~2 km from the instrument when using measurements at low elevation angles 	<p>time and/or a homogeneous atmosphere. Alternatively, the displacement can be accounted for ¹³.</p> <p>Once an absolute calibration is established, a relative calibration with the background signals can be performed^{15, 11}</p>
Accuracy of existing products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MWRs alone: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statistical retrievals: 0.2 to 2 K within 4 km ²² - Regularization method (single-channel MWR): 0.2 to 1.5 K ^{19,21} up to 1 km - Up to 6 km altitude with Net1D, IPT: 0.5 to 1.5 K ^{3,4,5} - IRS alone: 0.2 to 1.0 K within 2 km - Raman Lidar: 0.5 K for 0-5 km and 1.5 K for 5-10 km with 30 min integration / 10 W @ 355 nm ^{16, 9} 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - for Raman Lidar (30 min integration / 10W@355 nm): Accuracy: 5-10% for entire troposphere; Precision: <5% below 5 km; <20% for 5-10 km ^{14, 16} - for DIAL: 0.1 to 0.8 g/kg up to 1km^{6,7} - MWR alone: 0.2 to 1.5 g/m3 ³ - IRS alone: 0.1 to 1.0 g/kg within 2 km
Uncertainty estimates existing?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>For MWRs alone:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Net1D chain: provides full error covariance matrix <input type="checkbox"/> IPT chain: provides full error covariance matrix <input type="checkbox"/> TROPoe chain: provides full error covariance matrix - <u>IRS alone:</u> TROPoe provides full error covariance matrix - <u>For synergistic retrievals:</u> TROPoe ¹ provides full error-covariance matrix 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>for DIAL:</u> yes - <u>for IRS alone:</u> TROPoe provides full error covariance matrix - <u>For MWRs alone:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Net1D chain: provides full error covariance matrix <input type="checkbox"/> IPT chain: provides full error covariance matrix <input type="checkbox"/> TROPoe chain: provides full error covariance matrix
Readiness for operation	<p>For MWRs: yes</p> <p>For IRS: yes</p> <p>Raman lidar: no (deployed units are still most of the time “home-made instruments”, homogenization in the calibration techniques are probably needed, first commercial instruments appear on the market, but validation of performance is still missing ¹⁶).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - for DIAL: close to operational maturity as few prototypes close to full commercial production have already been evaluated ⁶ - for IRS: yes - for MWR: yes <p>Raman lidar: no (deployed units are still most of the time “home-made instruments”, homogenization in the calibration techniques are probably needed. First commercial instruments are available, but validation of performance is missing ¹⁶.)</p>
Temporal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MWR (depends on scanning strategy): 2 to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DIAL: averaging time ~20 min

resolution	5 min averaging time typically every 20 minutes - IRS: 1-min, but 5-min is typical - Raman lidar: 5 min	- IRS: 1-min, but 5-min is typical - MWR: 1 second - Raman lidar: 5 min
Timeliness	- MWR (depends on scanning strategy): - < 20 min for statistical retrievals or OEM method - < 1 hour for OEM based on model forecast - IRS: < 5 min - Raman lidar: <10 min	- MWR and IRS < 5 min - DIAL: < 30 minutes - Raman lidar: <10 min
Data availability	- IRS: 24/7 in non-precipitating conditions and below optically thick clouds - MWR: 24/7 in non-heavy precipitation conditions Raman Lidar: 24/7 in non-precipitating conditions	- for DIAL: 24/7 - IRS: 24/7 in non-precipitating conditions and below optically thick clouds - MWR: 24/7 in non-precipitating conditions Raman Lidar: 24/7 in non-precipitating conditions
Data format	- MWR: netcdf, ASCII - IRS: netcdf - Raman lidar: custom	- for DIAL: ASCII and netcdf - IRS: netCDF - Raman lidar : custom

Products	Inversion strength and position
Instruments	- MWR - IRS
Accuracy requirements	- Not defined
Temporal resolution Requirements	- Not defined
Applications	- Good indicator of ABL stability and potential pollutants accumulation - Weather application (alerts): heavy convection / fog
End-Users	- Air quality agency - National Weather Services - Wind energy sector - Airports

	- Nuclear power plants
Existing algorithms	- Directly derived from the brightness temperature measurements: in development - Derived from the retrieved temperature profile: available (manufacturer software for single-channel MWR, and TROPOe ¹ for other instruments)
Assumptions needed	- For MWR: horizontal homogeneity in area around ~2 km from the instrument when using measurements at low elevation angles
Accuracy of existing products	- in development
Uncertainty estimates existing?	- no
Readiness for operation	- Further evaluation of the products are necessary but used instrumentation is operational (MWR and IRS)
Temporal resolution	- MWR (depends on scanning strategy): 2 to 5 min averaging time typically every 20 minutes - IRS: 1-min, but 5-min is typical
Timeliness	- MWR (depends on scanning strategy): - < 20 min for statistical retrievals or OEM method - < 1 hour for OEM based on model forecast - IRS: < 5 min
Data availability	- IRS: 24/7 in non-precipitating conditions and below optically thick clouds - MWR: 24/7 in non-heavy precipitation conditions
Data format	- IRS: netcdf - MWR: graphics possible or custom format

4 REFERENCES

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